

Focus on higher degree research students through the ‘culture change’ looking glass

An implementation project for the Institutional Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

Macquarie University

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About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

In September 2021, Macquarie University released a [Research Data Management \(RDM\) Framework](#) which provided a foundation for changes in researcher behaviour and established mechanisms to ensure compliance, manage risk and enable best practice in RDM. The creation of this institutional RDM framework involved substantial organisational change in the approach to RDM and significant and coordinated action among stakeholders to enhance the environment for RDM at Macquarie University. The crux of the framework included a [detailed policy suite](#) outlining a comprehensive set of expected practices for managing data throughout the research data lifecycle accompanied by key improvements to infrastructure for both active and archived or published data.

Macquarie's participation in the ARDC Institutional Underpinnings (IU) program thus coincided with the execution of the early phases of the University's own [RDM for Institutions Framework](#) implementation project. Several institutional initiatives provided an essential foundation for responsible data management practices to be enacted by researchers. Increasing the adoption of new practices, however, required modification of individual and community behaviour. Substantial changes were desired in terms of researcher awareness and understanding of responsibilities and risks, as well as implementation of best practices - all considered to be key aspects of "culture change". Due to the effort and resources required for a shift of such magnitude, it was decided that support would be staged to specific cohorts of researchers, transitioning them to the new framework over 18 to 24 months. One of the first cohorts to be transitioned were new PhD researchers (commencing their studies after January 2022).

The culture change model initially adopted at Macquarie (in 2019) during the drafting of the RDM policy and development of supporting resources was the [Nosek model](#) which directly addressed change related to Open Research in universities. However, it was suggested in the [Research Data Management \(RDM\) for Institutions Framework](#) Culture Change element that the assumptions of the Nosek model might be too optimistic in the context of some Australian universities (i.e. the model assumed researchers already possessed the skills and motivation to make the required behavioural changes and that the role of university leadership was to create an environment to encourage researchers to do what they already wanted to do and knew how to do). For this reason, a more nuanced "culture change lens" was applied to help identify gaps in using the Nosek model and improve the approach. The hybrid model incorporated more universal and theory-based principles of change, as outlined in the [RDM for Institutions Framework](#) Culture Change element.

The initial phases of this project involved:

1. Articulating the culture change guiding principles (introduced in the [RDM for Institutions Framework](#) Culture Change element of the framework) that were considered most appropriate to the Macquarie context.
2. Identifying essential foundations for each principle of culture change that were addressed by the University prior to this project and ascertaining remaining elements which could feasibly be addressed during the timeframe of this project.

The above exercises highlighted several areas for enhancement in our approach to achieving culture change. For example, one challenge typically associated with culture change outlined in the RDM for Institutions Framework Culture Change element is that the current state needs to be clearly described, and measurable final state goals need to be defined as early as possible. Meaningful data must then be collected to evaluate change progress. Inadequate resourcing of teams, or lack of culture change experience by staff responsible for implementing RDM projects, means tracking the change process is an often-neglected component of culture change. Indeed, it was a milestone that could have easily been neglected due to workload constraints at Macquarie University.

To address these gaps:

3. Organisational perceptions of current state and desired target state from a self-assessment on the University's RDM services (via RISE) were explored.
4. An initial set of targets and accompanying metrics were established and measured (where possible in the timeframe) to help quantify or signal changes in RDM understanding, outlook and behaviour.

For the targeted HDR student cohort, the following 3 RDM culture change objectives were identified:

- A. HDR students are familiar with the RDM Policy and Procedure and can apply RDM knowledge to their own work.
- B. HDR students can successfully lodge DMPs for their research projects (that embody good practice).
- C. HDR students can define best practices in RDM and are engaging with documentation, training, and other resources designed to move RDM behaviours towards best practices. Several measures and indicators were selected and evaluated to assess progress against these three objectives over the timeframe of the Institutional Underpinnings Project:
 - Completion of RDMOnline training module
 - Results from pre- and post-surveys bookending the RDMOnline training module
 - Attendance in additional live training sessions
 - Successful lodgment of data management plans

- Usage of endorsed data storage platforms
- Requests for support and advice using the OneHelp ticketing system

Resulting Improvements

Current and target state were identified. An initial set of metrics was established and measured (where possible in the timeframe) to help quantify or signal changes in PhD students' RDM understanding, outlook and behaviour (to track progress towards the target state). The metrics revealed signs of positive changes in terms of RDM understanding and practices by HDR students at Macquarie University. Metrics will now more consciously and intentionally be employed as early as possible in subsequent work.

Next Steps

The measures used to track progress towards the target state identified were ones that could be collected and assessed in a short timeframe. Collection of other metrics is planned in the mid-long term. This is an endeavour that Macquarie plans to extend to other cohorts and sustain into the future.

To continue to drive culture change, the most tangible but substantial next steps being taken at Macquarie University are to:

1. Enhance RDM support for HDR students via a targeted campaign to increase HDR Supervisors RDM awareness and understanding.
2. Improve and expand the self-help resources.
3. Automate several steps for onboarding and orientation of HDR students and supervisors to RDM requirements.
4. Establish mid-project reminders and support for students to update their DMPs as well as an "off-boarding" process where succession is planned for any active data and lodgment is completed for archived data (to be completed during PhD examination process).
5. Determine mid-to-longer-term metrics to be recorded (for the HDR cohort and others).
6. Establish a reporting "dashboard" to systematically collect measures to track culture change in the HDR cohort (and others) across varying time scales.

There are encouraging signs of an emerging RDM culture at Macquarie University. Undertaking phases of assessment and continuous improvement is proving vital. The University intends to transition from discrete, project-based change implementation activities towards a business-as-usual model of improving RDM practices. Planning activities are now underway to identify key services, forecast and allocate resources, and prioritise deliverables, with attainment of our desired state expected to take several years.

Project Outputs

Reusable outputs produced include the following resources related to both the Macquarie University RDM Framework implementation and associated with this project. These and the [full case study/project report](#) are all available via OSF. <https://osf.io/mr9yj/>

1. Change management [literature review](#).
2. [DMP documents](#) including the form as a pdf, a “DMP User Guide” and mock examples of completed DMPs.
3. Questions for “[DMP Completion survey](#)” for process improvement.
4. [RDMOnline training program](#) in Articulate (SCORM files on request) & [test bank](#) for the quiz.
5. [Questions](#) for the “Pre-RDMOnline training” and “Post-RDMOnline training ” surveys
6. [FAIR Data Attitudes and Behavior Survey](#)

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).